

CREATIVITY OF MAKSUD SHEIKHZADE

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Poetry is a painful and difficult work on oneself. Maksud Sheikhzade is a talented poet, playwright, literary critic, translator, who made a significant contribution to the development of Uzbek literature of the twentieth century. In his poems, he abandons rhetoric and descriptive, focuses on creating an image of a simple man, on expressing his various feelings, experiences and revealing his spiritual world.

Maksud Matsumbek-oglu Sheikhzade was born in the homeland of the outstanding Azerbaijani poet Nizami, in the Ganja region, the city of Aktash, in the family of a progressive intellectual doctor. His father loved art and literature, was interested in history and philosophy. The young Maksud first heard about such luminaries of the word as Nizami, Firdousi, Navoi, Fusuli, A.S. Pushkin and M.Y. Lermontov in fascinating conversations with his father.

After graduating from the old school in Aktash, Maksud entered the Baku Pedagogical College in 1921. Here he attended lectures by such famous teachers and scientists as Huseyn Javid and Abdullah Shaik. Then Maksud taught in the Dagestan cities of Derbent Buinaksk, graduated from the Baku Pedagogical Institute in absentia.

Back in Azerbaijan, Maksud Sheikhzade is trying his hand in the field of artistic creativity. In 1921, his first poem "The Song of the Red Army Man" was published in the newspaper "Communist". In 1923, Sheikhzade's drama "The Revolution of April 28" was published in Azerbaijani, the play was staged on stage by amateur artists, but due to artistic weakness it was not re-published. In 1927, the first poem of Sheikhzade "The Folk Parable of Nariman" was published in the magazine "Maorif va Madaniyat" in Azerbaijan, which testified to the young poet's desire for a wide coverage of life, about his creative pursuits.

In Tashkent, Sheikhzade begins to write in Uzbek, continues his search in fiction. The fruit of the first creative searches is the poem "Tractor", published in 1929 in Uzbek in the newspaper "Shark Hakikati". Although the poem was weak artistically, it still testified that the young poet had set himself a noble goal - to glorify human labor. After that, books of poems by the young poet are printed one by one. These include the poetry collections "Worthy Guardian" (1932), "Ten Poems" (1933), "The Third Book" (1934), "Republic" (1935), "Twelve",

"New Devan" (1937), "Election Songs" (1938). These collections, which belong to the first period of Shehzade's creative career, were artistically immature and had many shortcomings.

The poet often expounded in poetic form some popular idea. At that time, most Soviet poets paid attention primarily to the social essence of poetry. Shehzade also followed this principle, he considered the poet a warrior of a new life, poetry - an important tool for creating a new world.

In the 30s, Sheikhzade gradually comprehends that poetry is a very complex and responsible art. Russian Russian classical literature and, especially, the work of V.V. Mayakovsky, Sheikhzade begins to use a free poetic system in his work and at the same time achieves a combination of the traditions of Russian and Eastern poetry.

Maksud Sheikhzade's creative search during the war years led to significant results. The most successful in artistic terms are the poems "The Eleventh", "Zhenya", "The Third Son".

Almost throughout his career, Sheikhzadeh was engaged in criticism and literary criticism. In 1948, he defended his PhD thesis on the artistic features of the lyrics of Alisher Navoi, publishes many scientific works on the work of the great Uzbek poet. These include such informative articles as "On the characteristics of the lyrical hero of Navoi" (1947), "On the artistic style of Navoi" (1958) "In the workshop of a mentor", "Sultan in the world of gazelles" (1960). Sheikh Zadeh's research on the works of Babur, Mukimiy, Furkat, Aibek, Gafur Gulyam and other Uzbek writers and poets is considered to be of great scientific value.

A significant part of Sheikhzade's work consists of artistic translations. He translated into Uzbek the play "Mozart and Saliers", the poem "The Bronze Horseman" by A.S. Pushkin, poems by Rustaveli, Nizami Ganjaviy, Fusuli, Mirza Fatali Akhundov, Shakespeare, Byron, Goethe, Aeschylus, Aesop.

Thus, thanks to his multifaceted talent, Maksud Sheikhzade took a worthy place among the major representatives of Uzbek literature of the twentieth century.

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